

NEW CONGRUENCES FOR PARTITIONS WHERE THE EVEN PARTS ARE DISTINCT

Hemjyoti Nath¹

Department of Mathematical Sciences, Tezpur University, Tezpur, Assam, India
msm22017@tezu.ac.in

Received: 5/14/23, Accepted: 8/14/24, Published:

Abstract

We denote the number of partitions of n wherein the even parts are distinct (and the odd parts are unrestricted) by $ped(n)$. In this paper, we will use generating function manipulations to obtain new congruences for $ped(n)$ modulo 24.

1. Introduction and Main Result

A partition of a positive integer n is a non-increasing sequence of positive integers whose sum is equal to n . If $p(n)$ denotes the number of partitions of a positive integer n and we adopt the convention $p(0) = 1$, then the generating function for $p(n)$ satisfies the identity

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p(n)q^n = \frac{1}{(q; q)_{\infty}},$$

where

$$(a; q)_{\infty} := \prod_{n=0}^{\infty} (1 - aq^n), \quad |q| < 1.$$

Throughout this paper, we write

$$f_k := (q^k; q^k)_{\infty}, \quad \text{for any integer } k \geq 1.$$

The number of partitions of n wherein the even parts are distinct (and the odd parts are unrestricted) is denoted by $ped(n)$. The generating function for $ped(n)$ [6] is

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} ped(n)q^n = \frac{(-q^2; q^2)_{\infty}}{(q; q^2)_{\infty}} = \frac{(q^4; q^4)_{\infty}}{(q; q)_{\infty}}. \quad (1.1)$$

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13768812

¹This work is based on part of master's project at Tezpur University under the supervision of Prof. N.D. Baruah.

Note that by (1.1), the number of partitions of n wherein the even parts are distinct (and the odd parts are unrestricted) equals the number of partitions of n with no parts divisible by 4, i.e., the 4-regular partitions (see [6] and references therein). In recent years many congruences for the number of 4-regular partitions have been discovered (see [2–4, 11, 14–17] and references therein).

Numerous congruence properties are known for the function $ped(n)$. For example, Andrews, Hirschhorn and Sellers [6] proved that for $\alpha \geq 1$ and $n \geq 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} ped(3n + 2) &\equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \\ ped(9n + 4) &\equiv 0 \pmod{4}, \\ ped(9n + 7) &\equiv 0 \pmod{12}, \\ ped\left(3^{2\alpha+2}n + \frac{11 \cdot 3^{2\alpha+1} - 1}{8}\right) &\equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \\ ped\left(3^{2\alpha+1}n + \frac{17 \cdot 3^{2\alpha} - 1}{8}\right) &\equiv 0 \pmod{6}, \\ ped\left(3^{2\alpha+2}n + \frac{19 \cdot 3^{2\alpha+1} - 1}{8}\right) &\equiv 0 \pmod{6}. \end{aligned}$$

Recently, Xia [5] obtained many interesting infinite families of congruences modulo 8 for $ped(n)$.

The aim of this paper is to establish new congruences modulo 24 for $ped(n)$. In the next theorem, we state our main results.

Theorem 1.1. *For every $n \geq 0$, we have*

$$\begin{aligned} ped(225n + 43) &\equiv 0 \pmod{24}, \\ ped(225n + 88) &\equiv 0 \pmod{24}, \\ ped(225n + 133) &\equiv 0 \pmod{24}, \\ ped(225n + 223) &\equiv 0 \pmod{24}. \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, for every $k \geq 1$ and $n \geq 0$, we have

$$ped(9n + 7) \equiv ped\left(9 \cdot 5^{2k}n + \frac{57 \cdot 5^{2k} - 1}{8}\right) \pmod{24}.$$

The paper is organised as follows: In Section 2, we present some preliminaries required for our proofs. In Sections 3, we present the proof of Theorem 1.1.

2. Preliminaries

In this section, we collect the q -series identities that are used in our proofs. Recall that Ramanujan’s general theta function $f(a, b)$ [1] is defined by

$$f(a, b) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} a^{n(n+1)/2} b^{n(n-1)/2}, \quad |ab| < 1.$$

Important special cases of $f(a, b)$ are the theta functions $\varphi(q)$, $\psi(q)$ and $f(-q)$, which satisfies the identities

$$\varphi(q) := f(q, q) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} q^{n^2} = (-q; q^2)_{\infty} (q^2; q^2)_{\infty} = \frac{f_2^5}{f_1^2 f_4^2},$$

$$\psi(q) := f(q, q^3) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^{n(n+1)/2} = \frac{(q^2; q^2)_{\infty}}{(q; q^2)_{\infty}} = \frac{f_2^2}{f_1},$$

and

$$f(-q) := f(-q, -q^2) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{n(3n+1)/2} = (q; q)_{\infty} = f_1.$$

In terms of $f(a, b)$, Jacobi’s triple product identity [1] is given by

$$f(a, b) = (-a; ab)_{\infty} (-b; ab)_{\infty} (ab; ab)_{\infty}.$$

Lemma 2.1 (Hirschhorn [10]). *We have that*

$$f_1 = f_{25} (R(q^5) - q - q^2 R(q^5)^{-1}), \tag{2.1}$$

where

$$R(q) = \frac{(q; q^5)_{\infty} (q^4; q^5)_{\infty}}{(q^2; q^5)_{\infty} (q^3; q^5)_{\infty}}.$$

3. Proof of Theorem 1.1

Andrews, Hirschhorn and Sellers [6] proved that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} ped(9n + 7)q^n = 12 \frac{f_2^4 f_3^6 f_4^4}{f_1^{11}}. \tag{3.1}$$

Therefore,

$$ped(9n + 7) \equiv 0 \pmod{12}. \tag{3.2}$$

It follows from (3.1) that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} ped(9n + 7)q^n \equiv 12 \frac{f_2^4 f_3^6 f_4}{f_1^{11}} \pmod{24}. \tag{3.3}$$

But, by the binomial theorem, $f_t^{2m} \equiv f_t^m \pmod{2}$, for all positive integers t and m .

Therefore, it follows from (3.3) that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} ped(9n + 7)q^n \equiv 12f_1 f_6 f_{12} \pmod{24}. \tag{3.4}$$

Employing (2.1) in (3.4), we arrive at

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} ped(9n + 7)q^n \equiv & 12f_{25} f_{150} f_{300} \left(R_{30} R_5 R_{60} - R_{30} R_{60} q^2 - \frac{R_{30} R_{60} q^2}{R_5} + R_5 R_{60} q^6 \right. \\ & + R_{60} q^7 + \frac{R_{60} q^8}{R_5} - R_{30} R_5 q^{12} - \frac{R_5 R_{60} q^{12}}{R_{30}} + R_{30} q^{13} + \frac{R_{60} q^{13}}{R_{30}} \\ & + \frac{R_{30} q^{14}}{R_5} + \frac{R_{60} q^{14}}{R_{30} R_5} + R_5 q^{18} - q^{19} - \frac{q^{20}}{R_5} + \frac{R_5 q^{24}}{R_{30}} - \frac{R_{30} R_5 q^{24}}{R_{60}} \\ & - \frac{q^{25}}{R_{30}} + \frac{R_{30} q^{25}}{R_{60}} - \frac{q^{26}}{R_{30} R_5} + \frac{R_{30} q^{26}}{R_5 R_{60}} + \frac{R_5 q^{30}}{R_{60}} - \frac{q^{31}}{R_{60}} - \frac{q^{32}}{R_5 R_{60}} \\ & \left. + \frac{R_5 q^{36}}{R_{30} R_{60}} - \frac{q^{37}}{R_{30} R_{60}} - \frac{q^{38}}{R_{30} R_5 R_{60}} \right) \pmod{24}. \tag{3.5} \end{aligned}$$

Extracting the terms involving q^{5n+4} from both sides of (3.5), dividing both sides by q^4 and then replacing q^5 by q , yields

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} ped(9(5n + 4) + 7)q^n \equiv 12f_5 f_{30} f_{60} \left(2q^2 \frac{R_6}{R_1} - q^3 \right) \pmod{24},$$

from which it follows that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} ped(45n + 43)q^n \equiv 12q^3 f_5 f_{30} f_{60} \pmod{24}. \tag{3.6}$$

Next, equating the coefficients of q^{5n+j} on both sides of this congruence, where $j = 0, 1, 2, 4$, gives the congruences in Theorem 1.1.

Further, extracting the terms involving q^{5n+3} from both sides of (3.6), dividing both sides by q^3 and then replacing q^5 by q , yields

$$ped(225n + 178) \equiv 12f_1 f_6 f_{12} \pmod{24}.$$

which is equivalent to

$$ped(9n + 7) \equiv ped(225n + 178) \pmod{24}. \quad (3.7)$$

Successive iterations of (3.7) give

$$\begin{aligned} ped(9n + 7) &\equiv ped(9(25n + 19) + 7) \\ &\equiv ped(225(25n + 19) + 178) \\ &\equiv ped(9 \cdot 5^4 n + 9 \cdot 5^2 \cdot 19 + 9 \cdot 19 + 7) \\ &\quad \vdots \\ &\equiv ped(9 \cdot 5^{2k} n + 9 \cdot 19 \cdot 5^{2k-2} + \dots + 9 \cdot 19 + 7) \\ &\equiv ped\left(9 \cdot 5^{2k} n + \frac{57 \cdot 5^{2k} - 1}{8}\right) \pmod{24}. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof.

The author would like to end this section with the following conjecture:

Conjecture 3.1. For each nonnegative integer n ,

$$\begin{aligned} ped(225n + 43) &\equiv 0 \pmod{192}, \\ ped(225n + 88) &\equiv 0 \pmod{192}, \\ ped(225n + 133) &\equiv 0 \pmod{192}, \\ ped(225n + 223) &\equiv 0 \pmod{192}. \end{aligned}$$

4. Concluding Remarks

Recently, Chen [14] proved some vanishing results on the coefficients of $\theta_\chi(z)$ and the product of two theta functions. Using these results and some generating function manipulations we can find many more congruences for $ped(n)$ modulo 24.

Acknowledgement. The author thanks the referee for careful reading and useful suggestions.

References

- [1] B. C. Berndt, *Number Theory in the Spirit of Ramanujan*, AMS, Providence, 2006.
- [2] B. Dandurand and D. Penniston, ℓ -divisibility of ℓ -regular partition functions, *Ramanujan J.* **19** (2009), 63–70.

- [3] B. Gordon and K. Ono, Divisibility of certain partition functions by powers of primes, *Ramanujan J.* **1** (1997), 25–34.
- [4] D. Furcy and D. Penniston, Congruences for ℓ -regular partition functions modulo 3, *Ramanujan J.* **27** (2012), 101–108.
- [5] E. X. W. Xia, New infinite families of congruences modulo 8 for partitions with even parts distinct, *The Electronic Journal of Combinatorics* **21** (2014), 4–8.
- [6] G.E. Andrews, M.D. Hirschhorn and J.A. Sellers, Arithmetic properties of partitions with even parts distinct, *Ramanujan J.* **22** (2010), 273–284.
- [7] H. Dai, Congruences for the number of partitions and bipartitions with distinct even parts, *Discrete Math.* **338** (2015), 133–138.
- [8] H. Nath, The pod function and its connection with other partition functions, *Rad HAZU, Matematičke Znanosti*, to appear.
- [9] H. Nath, Parity results of PEND partition, preprint [arXiv:2407.10428](https://arxiv.org/abs/2407.10428).
- [10] M. D. Hirschhorn, *The power of q, a personal journey*, Developments in Mathematics **49**, Springer, 2017.
- [11] O. Y. M. Yao, New congruences modulo powers of 2 and 3 for 9-regular partitions, *J. Number Theory* **142** (2014), 89–101.
- [12] S. C. Chen, On the number of partitions with distinct even parts, *Discrete Math.* **313** (2013), 1565–1568.
- [13] S. C. Chen, The Number of Partitions with Distinct Even Parts Revisited, *Discrete Math.* **346** (2023), 133–138.
- [14] S. C. Chen, Partition congruences and vanishing coefficients of products of theta functions, *Ramanujan J.* **62** (2023), 1125–1144.
- [15] S. P. Cui and N. S. S. Gu, Arithmetic properties of ℓ -regular partitions, *Adv. Appl. Math.* **51** (2013), 507–523.
- [16] S. P. Cui and N. S. S. Gu, Congruences for 9-regular partitions modulo 3, *Ramanujan J.* **38** (2015), 503–512.
- [17] W. J. Keith, Congruences for 9-regular partitions modulo 3, *Ramanujan J.* **35** (2014), 157–164.